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KAUSHAL ELECTRONICS

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Abstract

The theory of special connectivity [1] has proposed a new theory for gravity in terms of Kaushal constant [2]. The paper shows the effect of this constant on the branch of electronics. Fundamental frequency of vibration has been calculated. Also, Values of charge, current, voltage, capacitance and inductance have been derived.

Keywords: Theory of Special Connectivity; Kaushal Constant; Electronics; Fundamental Frequency; Charge; Current; Voltage; Capacitance; Inductance.

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1. Introduction

Theory of special connectivity [1] has redefined gravity in terms of gravitational waves. Also, according to the Samaveda [3], the fundamental frequency of vibration is OM. Using this fact, an attempt has been made to calculate the value of OM. Also, using Kaushal constant [2] the governing gems of electronics have been derived.

2. Fundamental Frequency

Angular momentum is given by:

$$L = mav \tag{1}$$

Where, m is mass, a is radius and v is the velocity.

Also, Kaushal constant in terms of time is given by:

$$K = \frac{ma^2}{t} \tag{2}$$

Since, Kaushal constant is a type of angular momentum. Hence, from equation 1 and 2, we get:

$$v = \frac{a}{t} \quad (3)$$

The energy of gravitational waves is always quantised [2] and is given by:

$$E = Kf \quad (4)$$

Also, kinetic energy is given by:

$$E = \frac{mv^2}{2} \quad (5)$$

From equation 3, 4 and 5:

$$f = \frac{K}{2ma^2} \quad (6)$$

Where, f is the fundamental frequency of vibration, K is Kaushal constant, m is mass and a is radius.

Kaushal constant is given by:

$$K = \frac{mGh}{ga^2} \quad (7)$$

Where, m is mass, G is gravitational constant, h is plank's constant, g is acceleration due to gravity and a is radius.

3. Charge, Current and Voltage

According to the theory of special connectivity, energy is given by the formula:

$$E = \frac{K^2}{ma^2} \quad (8)$$

Also, time is given by:

$$t = \frac{ma^2}{K} \quad (9)$$

Since, $power = \frac{energy}{time}$

Hence power becomes:

$$P = \frac{K^2}{m^2a^4} \quad (10)$$

Also, power is given by:

$$P = I^2R \quad (11)$$

Using equation 10 and 11, we get:

$$I = \frac{K}{ma^2} \sqrt{\frac{K}{R}} \quad (12)$$

Where, I is current in terms of Kaushal constant and R is resistance.

$$\text{Also, charge is; } Q = it \quad (13)$$

Using equation 9 and 12, we get:

$$Q = \sqrt{\frac{K}{R}} \quad (14)$$

Where, Q is charge, K is Kaushal constant and R is resistance.

$$\text{Also, voltage is; } V = IR \quad (15)$$

Using equation 12, we get:

$$V = \frac{K}{ma^2} \sqrt{KR} \quad (16)$$

Where, V is voltage, K is Kaushal constant and R is resistance.

4. Capacitance

Capacitance is given by the formula:

$$C = \frac{Q}{V} \quad (17)$$

Hence, from equation 14 and 16, we get:

$$C = \frac{ma^2}{KR} \quad (18)$$

Where, C is capacitance, K is Kaushal constant and R is resistance.

5. Inductance

Inductance is given by the formula:

$$V = L \frac{dI}{dt} \quad (19)$$

Where, V is voltage, L is inductance and I current.

Using equation 12 and 16 in 19, we get:

$$L = \frac{2KR}{3ma^2} \quad (20)$$

Formula in equation 20 is dimensionally incorrect. Hence using equations of consciousness [1].

For quantum teleportation, equation of consciousness is $2=1$ and for human teleportation it becomes $2=-1$. We can consciously apply these equations since we know that the inductance formula is dimensionally incorrect.

Hence, the formula becomes after applying $1=-1$:

$$L = \frac{2}{3} \frac{ma^2}{K} R \quad (21)$$

Where, L is inductance, m is mass, R is resistance and K is Kaushal constant.

6. Value of OM

Let us now derive the value of OM:

Frequency of resonance (f_r) is given by the formula:

$$f_r = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{LC}} \quad (22)$$

Using equations 18 and 21 in 22, we get:

$$f_r = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \frac{K}{ma^2}} \quad (23)$$

Dividing equation 23 by 6, we get:

$$\frac{f_r}{f} = 0.3898 \quad (24)$$

Equation 24 means that human need to create a frequency in order of 0.3898 to match the resonating frequency with the fundamental frequency.

The fact stated in Samaveda says that the fundamental frequency of vibration is OM. Hence the value of OM becomes the ratio of the resonating frequency to the fundamental frequency and which is always equals to 0.3898 and can be defined as: $OM = 1/\pi \sqrt{3/2}$

7. Conclusion

Theory of special connectivity has been proved mathematically right. Fundamental frequency of vibration and gems of electronics like current, capacitance, inductance etc. have been derived. Value of OM is a point to be noted.

References

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